

JOSEPH OMOREGBE'S PHILOSOPHY OF CIVIL DISOBEDIENCE AND THE IMPERATIVENESS OF THE
2009 ASUU STRIKE: IMPLICATIONS FOR A SUSTAINABLE HIGHER EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The higher education sub-sector in the Nigerian educational system has experienced various set-backs in the recent past. The most memorable is the 2009 ASUU strike which held down academic activities in the nation's universities for over three months. It was yet one of such endless face-off between Academic Union of Universities (ASUU) and the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) as a result of the refusal of the FGN to sign an agreement reached between the duo in 2001. The strike apart from holding down academic activities in the federation, affected various aspects of the nation's socio-economic cum political lives. While some put blames on ASUU, others blamed the FGN. Though the strike was called off at the end, its consequential effects are still memorable. The aftermath of the strike is another thing to be worried about. The issues to contend with in this article therefore are: i) Will the 2009 ASUU strike be the last in the life of the country's higher education system? ii) Did the strike yield any positive or negative result? iii) Did ASUU achieve its aims of embarking on the strike? The outcome of the study reveals that both the FGN and ASUU were responsible for the incessant and prolonged strikes that have crippled the nation's tertiary education system. The study recommends among others that, the constitution and the Rule of Law should be guiding principles by both parties in order to safeguard the collapse of the nation's tertiary education system. The methodology adopted in this study is strictly the philosophical with Joseph Omoregbe's Philosophy of Civil Disobedience as the tool for evaluation.

KEYWORDS: Civil Disobedience, ASUU Strike, Insensibility, Sustainability, Higher Education

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of university education is to help produce competent work force that will help contribute to the growth and develop of the society in all spheres of life: educationally, economically, socially, religiously, politically and otherwise. This laudable goal of Nigerian universities cannot be, and have not been perfectly attained in the event of unstable university educational system in the Nigerian society as a result of government's insensitivity in directing required attention to the university education system in Nigeria. It is to curb this negligence, staff of Nigerian universities resort mostly, to the use of the non-violent instrument of civil disobedience (strike action) to drive home their demands which in-turn are geared towards a sustainable university system in Nigeria. Since when two elephants fight it is the grasses that suffer; the students and of course those who depend on the university community for their daily bread are adversely affected.

For instance, the 2009 ASUU strike which lasted for over three months though was peaceful, resulted in the loss of lives of some students: first those who had to travel back to their homes and some others who indulged in criminal activities as a result of the idleness imposed on them by the suspension of academic activities by university lecturers occasioned by government's nonchalance and insensitivity. In the same vein, the economic life of those who depended on the university system for survival was crippled. Likewise, expectations of parents and guardians were caught short, as the expected years of their ward(s)' graduation was becoming a mirage.

Certain salient issues were raised in the course of the length of the 2009 ASUU strike: while some questioned the rationale for the strike, others were interested in the outcome. Similarly, some others pondered on the consequential effect of the strike to the students, the lecturers, the government and the larger society.

Since research undertakings are aimed at proffering solutions to problems, this researcher is interested in critically examining the contending issues as highlighted earlier to investigate the legality and rationality of the 2009 AUU strike and proffer lasting solutions towards achieving a sustainable university education in the country. While employing the philosophical approaches of analyses, applications and speculation, the study will adopt Joseph Omoregbe's Philosophy of Civil Disobedience as the instrument of judgment.

WHAT IS CIVIL DISOBEDIENCE?

According to the Encarta Dictionaries (2008), civil disobedience means “the deliberate breaking of a law by ordinary citizens, carried out as nonviolent protest or passive resistance”. The Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English (2003) defined civil disobedience as “when people, especially a large group of people, refuse to obey a law in order to protest in a peaceful way against the government”. To Omoregbe (1994) “Civil disobedience is the right of the individual or group of people to oppose unjust and oppressive positive laws”.

Civil disobedience cannot be adequately discussed without making reference to Thoreau (1848) who stated that, “people should not permit governments to overrule or atrophy their consciences, and that people have a duty to avoid allowing such acquiescence to enable the government to make them the agents of injustice”. He gave this advice when he gave a lecture titled “The Rights and Duties of the Individual in relation to Government”.

The term “civil disobedience” however was made popular in 1849, when he (Thoreau) published an article titled: “*Resistance to Civil Government*” in a magazine with the title; *Aesthetic Papers*. According to Buber Martin (1962) “This essay was later reprinted in a collection of Thoreau's work (*A Yankee in Canada, with Anti-Slavery and Reform Papers*) under the title *Civil Disobedience*, by which it is most popularly known today”.

In defining what civil disobedience, one may be interested to know why it must be termed civil disobedience, why not public disobedience? The word *civil* in this context connotes that which is “relating to citizens and their interrelations with one another or with the state”, while disobedience from its natural meaning has to do with “not adhering to a giving instruction”. In this context therefore, *civil disobedience* implies “disobedience to the state authorities”. Civil in this context does not mean, “Adhering to or observing accepted social forms or being polite”.

Civil disobedience had been employed by several notable persons all over the world to check the excesses of governments. Among such persons include the popular former American civil-rights leader Dr. Martin Luther King, Jr. During the 1950s and 60s he led numerous peaceful marches, boycotts, and sit-ins in the United States of America which made him to achieve international fame. Another apostle of civil disobedience is Mohandas Gandhi an Indian then in South Africa who employed civil disobedience to gain Indian rights in South Africa and later won independence for India. Gandhi developed the idea of *satyagraha* which means “holding to truth” *Satyagraha* is an act of civil disobedience marked by Indians and it is characterized by high moral standards and sense of self-discipline. Attracting a huge number of followers from the Indian public, Gandhi was able to use the technique as an effective political tool and play a key role in bringing about the British decision to end colonial rule of his homeland.

JOSEPH OMORGBE'S PHILOSOPHY OF CIVIL DISOBEDIENCE: AN OVERVIEW

Omoregbe started his philosophy of civil disobedience by stating that civil disobedience is a right enshrined in the natural law and is to be enjoyed by citizens of a state. As a natural right therefore, its violation by constituted authorities, results when such authority promulgates a law, enacts a decree or formulates a policy that is at variance with the natural law or right of the common-man, especially when such law is intended to frustrate the right of the citizenry to civil disobedience. As Omoregbe rightly puts it; “Citizens have the right to arrest any attempt by the state to deprive them of their natural rights through legislation, decree or by any other means.” From the foregoing therefore, in any state or society, those in authority tend to deliberately make laws (positive laws) or policies that are at variance with the natural law. Natural laws are God-given; as such any other positive law that goes contrary to the natural law becomes null and void and can be disobeyed.

Arguing further, Omoregbe stated that, “... when two laws are in conflict, the higher one overrides the lower one which automatically becomes null and void and loses its binding force” This is also the viewpoint of Lloyd (1964) when he opined that:

Not only does such a higher law override and nullify the actual rules of a particular society which are shown to violate it, but it follows from this conclusion that the individual citizen may be relieved from his duty to comply with the actual law, and even possess a lawful basis for revolt against the legitimate authority of the state.

One of the rights to be enjoyed by the citizens of a country (Nigeria inclusive), is to resist oppression. As such, ASUU's reaction to government's nonchalance could be reasoned to mean an attempt to resist government

oppression of not trying to implement an earlier agreed term. But the question is this: did ASUU follow the due processes of civil disobedience?

Omogbe in his philosophy of civil disobedience suggested a procedural three steps of action to be considered before embarking on such action:

- i. The first step that citizens should take in such a situation of conflict between the natural law and the government law or policy is to point out to the government that its law (or policy) is in conflict with the natural law. This should be done in a number of ways: it could be through writing ...
- ii. If, however the government (king, emperor, president, Prime Minister, as the case May be) having been informed that its law is in conflict with the natural law, continuous to insist on its observance, the citizens should simply let the government know that they are morally obliged to obey God (nature) rather than man. That is, to obey the natural law (a higher law) rather than its own law; which is in conflict with it.

This viewpoint is supported by Fellman (1971) who described such laws or policies as “violative acts” and the show of “raw powers”

- iii. If government goes on to use brute force – the police force, the military force or any other force, to compel the citizens to comply with the immoral, unjust or oppressive law or policy, then it has gone out of the realm of legality, civility, legitimacy and reasonableness and has resorted to brute force

Critically examining the strike it is obvious that ASUU exhausted all the available avenues before embarking on the strike. There were negotiations and renegotiations between 2001 and 2009, there were also series of warnings in the form of writing an ultimatum, etc which suffice the three steps prescribed by Omogbe.

OBJECTIVES OF CIVIL DISOBEDIENCE

According to Omogbe (1994), civil disobedience is not intended at all for ulterior political ambition. It is not an act directed towards change of government, neither is it meant to overthrow incumbent government, nor is it aimed at arousing civil unrest for effective lawlessness. As he rightly puts it:

The aim of Civil Disobedience is not, of course, to overthrow the government or to cause a breakdown of law and order in the society. The aim is to persuade the government in a peaceful manner to withdraw an unjust, or oppressive policy, or to repeal a law that is in conflict with the natural law- an unjust or oppressive law, in the interest of justice, peace and happiness of the citizens. This is the ultimate aim of civil disobedience, and this is why it has to be carried out in a peaceful manner, never in a violent manner.

From this viewpoint of Omogbe, it is evident that, the intention of civil disobedience is to make government reconsider or abrogate its unjust laws, policies and decisions (nonchalance in this case) which are at variance with the natural law.

One is compelled to agree with Omogbe that if civil disobedience has ulterior motive, it is no longer civil disobedience but sabotage which is itself illegal and of course morally unacceptable. In the same vein, if civil disobedience is not peaceful protest but destructive and harmful, then it has become rivalry party in disguise and the instrumentation to antagonism and lawlessness. In this case, government will be justified to defend itself against this internal enemy.

As emphasized by Omogbe, the ultimate purpose and reason for civil disobedience must be to persuade government to renege from its initial unfriendly decision, law or policy for the benefit of all. No wonder ASUU went into negotiation and renegotiation stages with the FGN among other persuasive means.

THE 2009 ASUU STRIKE AND OMOREGBE'S PHILOSOPHY OF CIVIL DISOBEDIENCE: ANY DEVIANCE?

The intrinsic and essential elements of civil disobedience, for Joseph Omogbe include legality, peacefulness, common good, public act, due process and persuading government to withdraw or compromise its position. Critically analyzing the nature of the 2009 ASUU strike, does it fulfill the above conditions of civil disobedience?

To be precise, was the strike legal? Was it a public act? Was it for the common good of all in the society? Was it peaceful? In sum, did the 2009 ASUU strike meet all the essentials of civil disobedience as postulated by Joseph Omoregbe? These fundamental questions shall be technically resolved as we examine the *a priori* and *a posteriori* conditions of the strike.

The Legality of the Strike

To establish the legality of the 2009 ASUU strike, one is tempted to ask if the strike was a right of the lecturers. According to Hogan (2006), a right is “a legitimate or socially recognized moral to or legal justification for an individual to be allowed specific behavior or to demand specified behaviour of others with regards to himself.” Omoregbe (1994) stated that the chapter four of the Nigerian 1999 Constitution deals with Human Rights and draws a good deal from the “Universal Declaration of Human Rights” as promulgated by the General Assembly of the United Nations in 1948. A critical perusal of the Nigerian constitution indicates that civil disobedience is legal. This legality therefore makes it a right of any citizen of the country, ASUU inclusive. This legality of civil disobedience makes it a right of the Nigerian University lecturers to embark on such strike if all the prescribed steps have been exhausted. Since the 2009 strike was an aspect of civil disobedience, it was therefore legal and of course, a right of the Nigerian universities’ lecturers.

The Necessity of the 2009 Strike

Many viewpoints have been severally raised as to whether the strike was necessary or not. As Nwandu (2009) puts it, “ASUU should be blamed for the lingering strike[...] if they are not contented with what government is offering they should look elsewhere for their source of income” According to Egwu (2009): “Only suspension of the strike by ASUU can facilitate discussion with its officials”. In the view of Kayode (2009) “there is a limit to rigidity in any demand”

The above views among others appear very convincing and one may be tempted to agree that the 2009 ASUU strike was unnecessary and over prolonged. And that ASUU was too rigid in its decision. However, a critical introspection into the following arguments will convince one that the strike was unequivocally pertinent and necessary for the general growth and development of the Nigerian society:

i. The Federal Government’s 7-points Agenda and Vision 20:2020

The products of the universities are the future man power of the country that will contribute to the achievement of the Federal Government’s 7-point agenda and vision 2020. But how could these agenda of government be achieved in the nearest future when academic activities in the universities would be left uncared for by the same government? To this end Eneuvie (2009) decried:

You know! It is a sad truth that our government is yet to realize the importance of education in national development. A country that wishes to develop cannot do so without recognizing the place of education and if the government really wants to achieve its lofty dream of “Vision 2020”, then it must radically begin to revolutionize its values and reorder its priority in so far as education is concerned;

ASUU is not strike crazy. The future of the nations education needed to be protected and university lecturers who are the custodians of this education needed to protect it hence they have to utilize strike as a tool after every other means have failed to check government’s excesses.

ii. To Avoid the Unilateral Abrogation of the 2001 Agreement

The 2001 bilateral agreement between ASUU and the FGN was not an imposition on either party. Both parties conscientiously entered into the agreement after various meetings, negotiations and renegotiations, consultations, debates, etc. As such if the FGN refused to sign the agreement, it will amount to the unilateral abrogation of the agreement. It was to avoid this unilateral abrogation of the agreement which of course was a form of oppression and needed to be checked, that the 2009 strike was effected.

iii. Re-positioning the University Educational System

University education and education in general in Nigeria is said to be falling in standard. For instance, research has shown that no Nigerian University is ranked among the world’s first 1000 universities. Even in the so-called “jet age”, Nigeria is still referred to as a developing country after several decades of its independence and as the “Giant

of Africa.” This backwardness can only be checked when the University education system is stable, dependable and adequately sustained. Consequent upon this, the 2009 strike was a necessary tool to make the government sign the agreement and to avoid related strike actions in the country to avoid any set-back to the education sector.

ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE 2009 ASUU STRIKE

The three months strike embarked upon by academic staff of Universities, did it yield any positive result? Before considering the achievements of the strike, one cannot easily forget the efforts of the former labour leader, Adams Oshiomole who was able to bring the two parties together to the negotiation table to reach consensus, and which of course lead to the eventual signing of the most contentious agreement on Wednesday, 21 October 2009. Although many negative effects resulted from the strike, one cannot rightly say that ASUU’s demand was not met.

To recount the laudable achievements of ASUU, Idoko (2009) highlighted the following achievements and were summarized by the researcher:

- i. The minimum allocation of 26 percent of the annual budget to education as prescribed by UNESCO was implemented.
- ii. Autonomy was granted to the universities as demanded by the union.
- iii. A 70 years retirement age for universities’ professors was approved which was also part of ASUU demands.
- iv. Considering the dynamic nature of education, a proposal for the amendment of the JAMB Act, National Minimum Standard and Establishment of Institutions Act and the National Universities Commission (NUC) Act 2004 were forwarded to the National Assembly.
- v. ASUU also clarified that that the agreement was binding on all Universities-State of Federal. An indication that their demand was not one-sided.
- vi. Before the strike was even called-off, the Education Trust Fund (ETF) was refocused by government to specifically intervene in providing enabling environment for teaching and learning in Nigerian tertiary institutions. For instance, the sum of N4 billion was approved, to be funded by the ETF, as special intervention fund for the upgrading of six universities with one selected from each of the six geopolitical zones in the country.

It is pertinent to note here that the 2009 ASUU strike was not intended to benefit the educational sector only but for the overall wellbeing of all in the society. The fact is that education is the life-wire of the development of any human society. Any authority of a state or society that claims to be developing its society without any tangible impact on the education sector is doomed to fail. ASUU went on strike so that the problems in the education sector (universities) should be solved once and for all. And since the government became adamant and insensitive to that fact they have to use civil disobedience as a tool to check the government. Of course the results were laudable and the vision 2020 of the Federal government can now be made possible, as education will lay the foundation for its possibility and success.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This paper has been able to examine the 2009 ASUU strike taking into consideration its legality and necessity in relation to Joseph Omoregbe’s Philosophy of Civil Disobedience. The research revealed that although strikes are the right of citizens and are means of making government to compromise her decision and to effect justice, it has a lot of negative effects on the society as a whole and on the university system. Based on this revelations and discovery therefore, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Before policies are made by government or any authority, the masses should be adequately carried along by sending memoranda to seek their contributions and suggestions and their views be judiciously considered.
- ii. The rule of law should be the guiding principle to all since no one is above the law. In other words, both ASUU and the FGN should respect the rule of law.
- iii. The Constitution should be well consulted before making any policy for the citizens.
- iv. Citizenship as an academic course should be made compulsory at all levels of the nation’s education to educate the public of their rights.
- v. Philosophy of Law should be made a compulsory course in all tertiary institutions.

- vi. Specifically, government should place priority on the development of University education; university functionaries on their part should try to be considerate in their demands in order to achieve a sustainable university system in the country.
- vii. ASUU on their part should also endeavor to gain financial independence on their own through the production of goods and services for self sustenance.
- viii. Government should promptly hold on to agreements reached between her and workers to avoid breakdown of law and order in the public service.
- ix. Financial autonomy should be granted to all universities to enable them cater for their problems.

It is sincerely believed that if the above recommendations are considered, strike and other civil disturbances will be reduced to the barest minimum if not totally eradicated.

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